

Supplemental Material

Modeling calcium and magnesium balance: Effects of diuretics

Pritha Dutta¹ and Anita T Layton^{1,2,3,4*}

¹Department of Applied Mathematics, University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON N2L 3G1, Canada

²Department of Biology, University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON N2L 3G1, Canada

³Cheriton School of Computer Science, University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON N2L 3G1, Canada

⁴School of Pharmacology, University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON N2L 3G1, Canada

* Corresponding author

Table S1: Description and values of all model parameters

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Reference
Plasma volume	V_p	4.5 L	(1)
PTH			
Maximal rate constant of PTH secretion from the parathyroid gland	β_{exo}^{PTHg}	1.034 min ⁻¹	estimated ((2) and Fig. S2)
Factor controlling the maximal PTH secretion at a given plasma Ca ²⁺ concentration	γ_{Ca}	0.15 mM	estimated ((2) and Fig. S2)
Factor controlling the maximal PTH secretion at a given plasma Ca ²⁺ concentration	γ_p	2	estimated ((2) and Fig. S2)
Factor controlling the slope of the PTH secretion curve	C_m	3.8 mM	estimated ((2) and Fig. S2)
IC ₅₀ value of Mg ²⁺ for inhibition of PTH secretion	K_{low-Mg}	0.25 mM	(3)
Basal rate of PTH production in the parathyroid gland	k_{prod}^{PTHg}	2.53 pmol/min	estimated
Inhibition of PTH synthesis by 1,25(OH) ₂ D ₃	$\gamma_{prod}^{1,25(OH)_2D_3}$	0.003 pM ⁻¹	(4)

Rate of degradation of PTH in parathyroid gland	k_{deg}^{PTHg}	0.035 min ⁻¹	(5)
Degradation rate constant of plasma PTH	k_{deg}^{PTHp}	0.11 min ⁻¹	estimated
Vitamin D₃			
Inactive vitamin D ₃	$[25(OH)D]_p$	75 nM	(6)
Minimum production rate constant of 1,25(OH) ₂ D ₃	k_{conv}^{min}	4.4 x 10 ⁻⁶ min ⁻¹	(5)
Maximal increase in 1,25(OH) ₂ D ₃ production rate	δ_{conv}^{max}	6 x 10 ⁻⁵ min ⁻¹	(5)
Stimulation of 1,25(OH) ₂ D ₃ production by PTH	K_{conv}^{PTH}	3 pM	(5)
PTH sensitivity coefficient	n_{conv}	6	(5)
Inhibition of 1,25(OH) ₂ D ₃ production by Ca ²⁺	γ_{conv}^{Ca}	0.3 mM ⁻¹	(5)
Inhibition of 1,25(OH) ₂ D ₃ production by itself	$\gamma_{conv}^{1,25(OH)_2D_3}$	1.8 x 10 ⁻² pM ⁻¹	(5)
Factor controlling the maximal increase in 1,25(OH) ₂ D ₃ production by Mg ²⁺	δ_{Mg-act}	6.6	estimated ((7) and Fig. S1)
Michaelis-Menten constant	K_{Mg-act}^1	1.1 mM	estimated ((7) and Fig. S1)
Michaelis-Menten constant	K_{Mg-act}^2	1.2 mM	estimated ((7) and Fig. S1)
Inhibition of 1,25(OH) ₂ D ₃ degradation by PTH	γ_{inact}^{PTH}	0.52 pM ⁻¹	(5)
Michaelis-Menten constant	K_{D_3}	1.7 mM	estimated
Degradation rate constant of 1,25(OH) ₂ D ₃	$k_{deg}^{1,25(OH)_2D_3}$	0.008 min ⁻¹	estimated
Kidneys			
Glomerular filtration rate (GFR)	Φ_{GFR}	100 mL/min	(8)

Minimal fractional reabsorption of Mg^{2+} in proximal tubule	λ_{Mg-PT}^0	0.185	(9)
Stimulation of Mg^{2+} reabsorption in proximal tubule by PTH	δ_{Mg-PT}^{max}	0.015	assumed
Minimal fractional reabsorption of Ca^{2+} in proximal tubule	λ_{Ca-PT}^0	0.66	(10)
Stimulation of Ca^{2+} reabsorption in proximal tubule by PTH	δ_{Ca-PT}^{max}	0.03	assumed
Sensitivity of Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} reabsorption in proximal tubule to PTH	PTH_{ref}	12 pM	(5)
Hill coefficient	n_{PT}	5	(5)
Minimal fractional reabsorption of Mg^{2+} in thick ascending limb	λ_{Mg-TAL}^0	0.66	(9)
Stimulation of Mg^{2+} reabsorption in thick ascending limb by CaSR	$\delta_{Mg-CaSR}^{max}$	0.028	assumed
Stimulation of Mg^{2+} reabsorption in thick ascending limb by PTH	δ_{Mg-PTH}^{max}	0.012	assumed
Minimal fractional reabsorption of Ca^{2+} in thick ascending limb	λ_{Ca-TAL}^0	0.185	(9)
Stimulation of Ca^{2+} reabsorption in thick ascending limb by CaSR	$\delta_{Ca-CaSR}^{max}$	0.011	assumed
Stimulation of Ca^{2+} reabsorption in thick ascending limb by PTH	δ_{Ca-PTH}^{max}	0.0045	assumed
Sensitivity of Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} reabsorption in thick ascending limb to Ca^{2+}	Ca_{ref}	1.25 mM	(11)
Sensitivity of Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} reabsorption in thick ascending limb to Mg^{2+}	Mg_{ref}	2.5 mM	(11)
Hill coefficient	n_{TAL}	4	(5)

Sensitivity of Mg^{2+} reabsorption in thick ascending limb to PTH	K_{TAL}^{PTH}	4 pM	(4)
Minimal fractional reabsorption of Mg^{2+} in distal tubule	λ_{Mg-DT}^0	0.08	(9)
Stimulation of Mg^{2+} reabsorption in distal tubule by PTH and $1,25(OH)_2D_3$	δ_{Mg-DT}^{max}	0.02	assumed
Minimal fractional reabsorption of Ca^{2+} in distal tubule	λ_{Ca-DT}^0	0.08	(9)
Stimulation of Ca^{2+} reabsorption in distal tubule by PTH and $1,25(OH)_2D_3$	δ_{Ca-DT}^{max}	0.02	assumed
Sensitivity of Mg^{2+} reabsorption in distal tubule to PTH	K_{DCT}^{PTH}	7.25 pM	(4)
Sensitivity of Mg^{2+} reabsorption in distal tubule to $1,25(OH)_2D_3$	$K_{DCT}^{1,25(OH)_2D_3}$	160 pM	(4)
Intestine			
Dietary Mg^{2+} intake	I_{Mg}	0.012 mmol/min	(12)
Dietary Ca^{2+} intake	I_{Ca}	0.017 mmol/min	(12)
Maximal rate of active absorption of Mg^{2+}	V_{active}	0.764 μ mol/min	(13)
Stimulation of active Mg^{2+} absorption by dietary Mg^{2+} intake	K_{active}	1.7 μ mol /min	(13)
Stimulation of Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} absorption by $1,25(OH)_2D_3$	$K_{abs}^{1,25(OH)_2D_3}$	100 pM	(5)
Bones			
Rate of Mg^{2+} uptake from plasma by fast bone pool	k_{p-f}^{Mg}	0.074 min^{-1}	estimated
Rate of Mg^{2+} release from fast bone pool to plasma	k_{f-p}^{Mg}	$0.2 \times 10^{-3} min^{-1}$	estimated
Rate of accretion of Mg^{2+} into the slow bone pool	γ_{ac}^{Mg}	$3.98 \times 10^{-4} min^{-1}$	estimated

Rate of Ca^{2+} uptake from plasma by fast bone pool	k_{p-f}^{Ca}	0.12 min^{-1}	estimated
Rate of Ca^{2+} release from fast bone pool to plasma	k_{f-p}^{Ca}	$0.27 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$	estimated
Rate of accretion of Ca^{2+} into the slow bone pool	γ_{ac}^{Ca}	$6.65 \times 10^{-4} \text{ min}^{-1}$	estimated
Minimal resorption rate	τ_{res}^{min}	0.142×10^{-3} mmol/min	(5)
Maximal resorption rate	δ_{res}^{max}	0.7×10^{-3} mmol/min	(5)
Stimulation of bone resorption by PTH	K_{res}^{PTHp}	2.45 pM	(5)
Stimulation of bone resorption by $1,25(\text{OH})_2\text{D}_3$	$K_{res}^{1,25(\text{OH})_2\text{D}_3}$	160 pM	(5)
Plasma			
Fraction of magnesium bound to proteins	κ_{b-Mg}	0.3	(14)
Fraction of calcium bound to proteins	κ_{b-Ca}	0.4	(5)

Table S2: Initial conditions

	Initial value	Range	Reference
$[PTH]_g$, pM	35		
$[PTH]_p$, pM	6.2	1.6-6.9	(15)
$[1,25(OH)_2D_3]_p$, pM	145	50-150	(6)
$[Mg^{2+}]_p$, mM	0.64	0.46-0.66	(16)
$[Ca^{2+}]_p$, mM	1.23	1.0-1.26	(16)
N_{Ca_f} , mmol	75		(17); calculations shown below
N_{Ca_s} , mmol	23750		(17); calculations shown below
N_{Mg_f} , mmol	174		calculations shown below
N_{Mg_s} , mmol	347		calculations shown below

Fast and slow bone pool Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} (N_{Ca_f} , N_{Ca_s} , N_{Mg_f} , and N_{Mg_s}) initial value

calculations

Mass of 1 mol of Ca^{2+} = ~40 g

Ca^{2+} content in fast bone pool (N_{Ca_f}) = 3 g (17)

$$= 3/40 * 1000 = 75 \text{ mmol}$$

Ca^{2+} content in slow bone pool (N_{Ca_s}) = 950 g (17)

$$= 950/40 * 1000 = 23,750 \text{ mmol}$$

An adult body contains approximately 25 g Mg^{2+} , with 50% to 60% present in the bones (18).

Mass of 1 mol of Mg^{2+} = ~25 g

Total Mg^{2+} content in bones = 13000 mg = 13 g = $13/25 * 1000 = 520$ mmol

Now, one-third of skeletal Mg^{2+} is surface limited and exchangeable (19).

Mg^{2+} content in fast pool (N_{Mg_f}) = $1/3 * 520$ mmol = 174 mmol

Mg^{2+} content in slow pool (N_{Mg_s}) = $2/3 * 520$ mmol = 347 mmol

Table S3: Baseline and inhibition reabsorption values for Mg²⁺ and Ca²⁺. Transport values are given in pmol/min. Percentage changes from baseline values are shown in parentheses.

	PT transport		TAL transport		DT (DCT+CNT) transport	
	Mg ²⁺	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	Ca ²⁺
Baseline	3.2	26	10	7.7	1.04	3.2
Loop diuretics						
NKCC2-70	3.2 (0%)	26 (0%)	8.76 (-12%)	6.14 (-20%)	1.42 (+36%)	3.71 (+16%)
NKCC2-100	3.48 (+9%)	28.8 (+11%)	4.87 (-51%)	-0.96 (-112%, backleak)	2.95 (+184%)	4.6 (+43%)
Thiazide diuretics						
NCC-70	3.2 (0%)	26 (0%)	10 (0%)	7.7 (0%)	1.02 (-2%)	3.86 (+21%)
NCC-100	3.58 (+12%)	29 (+12%)	9.98 (-0.2%)	7.67 (-0.3%)	0.35 (-66%)	2.84 (-11%)
K-sparing diuretics						
ENaC-70	3.2 (0%)	26 (0%)	10 (0%)	7.7 (0%)	1.15 (+11%)	4.13 (+29%)
ENaC-100	3.2 (0%)	26 (0%)	10 (0%)	7.7 (0%)	1.28 (+23%)	5.33 (+67%)

Fitting 1,25(OH)₂D₃ synthesis to experimental data

Figure S1: Comparison between experimental (7) and simulated changes in [1,25(OH)₂D₃]_p at different plasma Mg²⁺ concentrations. The **lsqcurvefit** function of MATLAB, which is a non-linear least-square solver, was used to fit our model simulations to experimental values.

Fitting PTH secretion to experimental data

Figure S2: Comparison between experimental (2) and simulated changes in PTH secretion at different plasma Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ concentrations. The **lsqcurvefit** function of MATLAB, which is a non-linear least-square solver, was used to fit our model simulations to experimental values.

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